

Viscosity B-Coefficient of Some Amino Acids in Water

O. P. AWASTHI and P. P. RASTOGI*

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow, India

Manuscript received 15 November 1978, revised 7 April 1980, accepted 25 August 1980

The viscosity B-coefficient of polyamino acids like DL-aspartic acid, DL-glutamic acid, L-histidine and L-arginine have been determined in aqueous solutions. The reported results indicate that the B values increase with the rise of temperature for aspartic and glutamic acids as compared to decrease observed for histidine and arginine; a novelty explained in terms of protic and aprotic i.e., structure breaking and making behaviour of these amino acids in water or a sort of proton transfer reaction occurring in such system.

THE proteins are high polyamides derived from monomers of α -amino carboxylic acids and are the principal building materials of skin, muscle, nerves, blood, enzymes, antibodies, hormones etc.; whereas the function of water is to maintain equilibrium in living system, by way of some unknown reversible biological processes. The imbalances produced in either of one beyond the reversibility of the process results in disorderness of the system and may cause serious hazards. Therefore, the role of a particular amino acid in water and its mechanism to control the functioning of the system is of utmost importance.

Thus, in view of the recent interest on account of their active role in biological processes, it would be desirable to study the mode of interaction, association and protonation of these amino acids in aqueous solutions. The present investigations are undertaken to determine coefficient B of Jones-Dole¹ viscosity equation, namely

$$\eta = \eta_0(1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC) \quad \dots (1)$$

for aspartic, glutamic, histidine and arginine in water at different temperatures to study proton transfer properties as well as to elaborate molecular processes occurring in such systems.

Experimental

DL-aspartic acid (99%) obtained from BDH (Biochemical) Chemicals Ltd., Poole, England and DL-glutamic acid, L-arginine and L-histidine CHR puriss (>99%) purchased from Fluka A. G. Buchs. S. G., Switzerland were used after drying in a vacuum desiccator.

Solutions were prepared on molar basis in conductivity water and were corrected for the changes in volume at other temperatures.

Density and viscosity measurements were carried out in a Toshniwal make Constant Temperature Bath maintained within a maximum temperature fluctuation of $\pm 0.02^\circ$. Density was determined with the help of a dilatometer and an Ubbelohde viscometer with a flow time of about 500 sec. for water was employed for measuring viscosity as described earlier^{2,3}.

The viscosity was calculated with the help of usual relation, namely:

$$\eta = \frac{d}{d_0} \times \frac{t}{t_0} \times \eta_0 \quad \dots (2)$$

From the viscosity data, the factors η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} ($\eta_{sp} = \frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0}$) were obtained for different solutions at various temperatures.

Results

The density and viscosity of DL-aspartic acid, DL-glutamic acid, L-histidine and L-arginine in water determined at different temperatures and concentrations are summarised alongwith η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} values in Tables 1,2,3 and 4 respectively. The factor η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} was plotted against \sqrt{C} at different temperatures. The plots are almost linear, the slopes of which give the values of B and are given in Table 5; whereas the ordinate intercepts give coefficient A, representing contribution from inter-ionic forces.

The coefficient A (for DL-aspartic : 0.006, DL-glutamic : 0.009, L-histidine : 0.008 and L-arginine : 0.014 at 25°) is found to be almost independent of temperature as well as 4-5% that of B values and therefore appears to be insignificant for detailed discussion.

* Alexander von Humboldt Fellow, Physikalisch-Chemisches Institut, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Theresienstr. 41, München, West Germany.

AWASTHI & RASTOGI : VISCOSITY B-COEFFICIENT OF SOME AMINO ACIDS IN WATER

TABLE 1—DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} VALUES OF DL-ASPARTIC ACID IN WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND CONCENTRATIONS

Conc. $C \times 10^2$ g. mole/lit	Density g/ml	Viscosity CP	η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} $(\eta_{sp} = \frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0})$
25°C			
0.00	0.9970	0.894	...
0.25	0.9971	0.894	0.014
1.00	0.9973	0.895	0.021
2.50	0.9980	0.897	0.026
5.00	0.9991	0.901	0.036
10.00	1.0016	0.907	0.048
30°C			
0.00	0.9956	0.801	...
0.25	0.9957	0.801	0.018
1.00	0.9960	0.803	0.026
2.50	0.9970	0.805	0.035
5.00	0.9979	0.809	0.046
10.00	1.0008	0.815	0.057
35°C			
0.00	0.9940	0.722	...
0.25	0.9942	0.723	0.025
1.00	0.9944	0.725	0.036
2.50	0.9954	0.727	0.043
5.00	0.9974	0.731	0.054
10.00	0.9984	0.739	0.071
40°C			
0.00	0.9922	0.656	...
0.25	0.9926	0.657	0.030
1.00	0.9928	0.659	0.040
2.50	0.9936	0.662	0.053
5.00	0.9954	0.666	0.065
10.00	0.9974	0.673	0.081

TABLE 3—DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} VALUES OF L-HISTIDINE IN WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND CONCENTRATIONS

Conc. $C \times 10^2$ g. mole/lit	Density g/ml	Viscosity CP	η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} $(\eta_{sp} = \frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0})$
25°C			
0.00	0.9970	0.894	...
0.25	0.9972	0.895	0.030
1.00	0.9973	0.898	0.048
2.50	0.9982	0.904	0.071
5.00	0.9994	0.913	0.098
10.00	1.0030	0.932	0.134
30°C			
0.00	0.9956	0.801	...
0.25	0.9957	0.802	0.025
1.00	0.9958	0.804	0.043
2.50	0.9970	0.809	0.063
5.00	0.9980	0.818	0.094
10.00	1.0010	0.833	0.123
35°C			
0.00	0.9940	0.722	...
0.25	0.9942	0.723	0.022
1.00	0.9943	0.725	0.040
2.50	0.9953	0.730	0.064
5.00	0.9965	0.737	0.089
10.00	0.9997	0.751	0.124
40°C			
0.00	0.9922	0.656	...
0.25	0.9924	0.657	0.021
1.00	0.9927	0.659	0.039
2.50	0.9936	0.662	0.059
5.00	0.9948	0.669	0.085
10.00	0.9978	0.680	0.113

TABLE 2—DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} VALUES OF DL-GLUTAMIC ACID IN WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND CONCENTRATIONS

Conc. $C \times 10^2$ g. mole/lit	Density g/ml	Viscosity CP	η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} $(\eta_{sp} = \frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0})$
25°C			
0.00	0.9970	0.894	...
0.25	0.9972	0.895	0.024
1.00	0.9982	0.897	0.040
2.50	0.9991	0.902	0.056
5.00	1.0000	0.909	0.078
10.00	1.0030	0.923	0.103
30°C			
0.00	0.9956	0.801	...
0.25	0.9959	0.802	0.030
1.00	0.9968	0.804	0.046
2.50	0.9977	0.808	0.058
5.00	0.9982	0.815	0.081
10.00	1.0020	0.828	0.108
35°C			
0.00	0.9940	0.722	...
0.25	0.9942	0.724	0.036
1.00	0.9951	0.726	0.049
2.50	0.9961	0.730	0.066
5.00	0.9968	0.736	0.086
10.00	1.0000	0.749	0.116
40°C			
0.00	0.9922	0.656	...
0.25	0.9924	0.657	0.040
1.00	0.9933	0.659	0.058
2.50	0.9947	0.664	0.073
5.00	0.9954	0.670	0.093
10.00	0.9984	0.682	0.124

TABLE 4—DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} VALUES OF L-ARGININE IN WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND CONCENTRATIONS

Conc. $C \times 10^2$ g. mole/lit	Density g/ml	Viscosity CP	η_{sp}/\sqrt{C} $(\eta_{sp} = \frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0})$
25°C			
0.00	0.9970	0.894	...
0.25	0.9974	0.895	0.033
1.00	0.9976	0.898	0.048
2.50	0.9982	0.902	0.070
5.00	0.9996	0.913	0.098
10.00	1.0010	0.930	0.128
30°C			
0.00	0.9956	0.801	...
0.25	0.9959	0.802	0.029
1.00	0.9961	0.808	0.045
2.50	0.9968	0.809	0.064
5.00	0.9981	0.817	0.092
10.00	0.9999	0.832	0.123
35°C			
0.00	0.9940	0.722	...
0.25	0.9944	0.723	0.025
1.00	0.9947	0.725	0.042
2.50	0.9952	0.729	0.061
5.00	0.9966	0.736	0.086
10.00	0.9992	0.750	0.117
40°C			
0.00	0.9922	0.656	...
0.25	0.9929	0.657	0.021
1.00	0.9932	0.659	0.039
2.50	0.9934	0.662	0.057
5.00	0.9951	0.668	0.083
10.00	0.9981	0.680	0.114

TABLE 5—VISCOSITY B-COEFFICIENT OF DL-ASPARTIC, DL-GLUTAMIC, L-HISTIDINE AND L-ARGININE IN WATER AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	DL-aspartic acid	DL-glutamic acid	L-histidine	L-arginine
25	0.13	0.29	0.39	0.36
30	0.15	0.31	0.38	0.34
35	0.17	0.32	0.37	0.33
40	0.19	0.33	0.35	0.32

Discussion

It may be noted from Table 5 that dB/dT is positive for acidic amino acids like aspartic and glutamic in contrast to negative for basic amino acids like histidine and arginine; the result can be explained in terms of protic and aprotic behaviour *i.e.*, structure breaking and making feature of these polyamino acids in water following the arguments of others^{4, 5, 6, 7, 8}.

Further, it may be pointed out that the existence of free carboxylic group in acidic amino acids capable of yielding proton in solution which can be easily solvated to give H₃O⁺ ion *i.e.*, resulting in protonation of water or a sort of disordering on account of the breaking of hydrogen bonded structure of water molecules, which obviously increases with the rise of temperature. Whereas in case of basic amino acids the free amino groups are responsible for the aprotic behaviour and can easily cause deprotonation of water molecules *i.e.*, long range ordering or a sort of enforcement of hydrogen bonded structure around these amino acids and therefore also accounts for the decrease in B values at higher temperatures.

The α-amino acids exist as zwitter ion in solution and their dissociation constants aspartic: 6.45 × 10⁻³ and glutamic: 8.3 × 10⁻³ have been reported, indicating the presence of free carboxylic

group enabling them to enter into protonation or deprotonation processes and can be expressed by the following mechanism:

(a) Protonation of water:

(b) Deprotonation of water:

An attempt has been made to corroborate and interpret these results in terms of thermodynamic parameter entropy which is defined as a measure of randomness *i.e.*, the decrease in entropy means ordering or structure making while an increase indicates disordering or structure breaking of the system.

Fig. 1. Hypothetical representation of Biological Process to occur in presence of amino acids.

Thus from above considerations it can be fairly demonstrated that the system attains higher entropy state for acidic amino acids as compared to lower entropy state for basic amino acids with rise of temperature and on account of the difference in entropy states a biological process to occur.

Finally, it may be concluded in general that the protons or "cations" are structure breakers as compared to structure promotion feature of "anions" in aqueous solutions and causes the biological process to occur in presence of acidic or basic amino acids with the rise or fall of temperature as shown in Fig. 1.

Acknowledgement

Mr. O. P. Awasthi is grateful to University Grants Commission for awarding Teachers-Fellowship under Faculty Improvement Programme and

to Dr. Tewarson, Principal, Lucknow Christian College for granting study leave. Thanks are also due to Prof. Ram Gopal for making us available polyamino acids.

References

1. G. JONES and M. DOLÉ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
2. P. P. RASTOGI and R. GOPAL, *Z. Physik. Chem. N. F.*, 1970, **69**, 1.
3. P. P. RASTOGI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1970, **43**, 2442.
4. R. W. GURNEY, 'Ionic Processes in Solution', McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York, 1953, p. 159.
5. M. KAMINSKY, *Discussion Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **24**, 150.
6. E. R. NIGHTINGALE, JR., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 894.
7. R. L. KAY, T. VITCUCCIO and D. F. EVANS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 2336.
8. D. FRANKS and K. G. LAWRENCE, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1966, 212.